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Impact Of Quality Of Instructional Resource On Teacher Training Process

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the impact of quality of instructional resource on teacher training process. The research work used descriptive survey design with a population of 550 students and a sample size of 100 derived by stratified disproportionate sampling technique. The study was guided by two research questions. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire by the researchers with 18-items measured on a modified 4-point likert scale. The instrument was validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument 0.83 was calculated using Cronbach-Alpha. Data analysis was done using mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that quality instructional resource produce high academic outcome in the learners, predicts effectiveness of the teachers tasks but also, the teacher should be aware of learner variables and have knowledge of prevailing situation where the resource is to be used. It was recommended that the teacher education management should do well to ensure that adequate space is provided for the storage of instructional resources for future use, the school management is also encouraged to put security in place to avert the theft of instructional resources provided for teaching and learning process, teacher educators should do well to be knowledgeable in learner variables in order to have a high performing class of students etc

Keywords: Quality instructional resource, training, teacher education

INTRODUCTION

The quality of instructional resource does have great impact on teaching and learning process and its effect on the learners especially in the areas of students engagement, comprehension and in the entire output of teaching and learning process is always something to look out for. This is due to the fact that quality instructional resources encourage interactive learning, accessible learning and relevant learning which produce knowledge and retention in the learner. Moreso, it brings about differentiation in diverse learning style ability of the students so that the teacher can provide needed support for the learning required. Thus, qualitative instructional resource is that which has the capacity to provide enhanced description and deep insight into a particular topic giving attention to definite, new and complex contents

to present facts, figures and many other perspectives in real world usage that permits comprehension and critical thinking by analysis and interpretation of given information for proper engagement with learning. Skarin (2019) perceives a quality instructional resource as that which is rich, intellectually demanding such that it creates gaps for further learning and motivation in learning, thus, it is given to analytical opportunity to open up the content for learning as well as accessible for contextualized learning. This therefore, points to the fact that a quality instructional resource has the potential to hold learners' attention and capable of producing a very deep level of learning effect. Then, it means it could be gleaned from here that a quality instructional resource is capable of making a learner engaged in critical thinking that would enhance deep learning. Bucolo (2020) explained that quality instructional resources should possess the following features like standard alignment, encourage rigorous instruction such that allows for meaningful and authentic learning, it should be useful to a wide range of students' abilities and to encourage sustained learning. The foregoing description presents that a quality instructional resource should be clear, adequately sequenced, adaptable to different styles of learning and ease of use in carrying out curriculum delivery. This means that the quality of an instructional resource is tied to the quality of instruction being given by the instructor at a given point in time and invariably tied to the quality of the instructor.

Instructional resource is another name for instructional material and it is dependent on the context of use. This is a tool that a teacher uses in carrying out instruction in the class or during a lesson delivery. According to Muraina (2015) instructional resources are human and non-human materials and facilities that eases, encourage, embellish and raise the standard of teaching and learning process. The Classroom Store (TCS, 2024) says that instructional resources are object or human beings that increase students' capacity to learn. It was further asserted that they have embedded information that meets determined learning needs, goals and educational targets. While (ACC, 2022) describe instructional resources as materials that pass information on the content of a subject based on the field of study, such that the curation aligns with desired outcomes. Based, on the definitions and descriptions given above, it only presents that instructional resources are enhancers of instructional delivery process and not the instruction itself and if every instructional resource is expected to be curated to match given subject matter, then, certain specific features must be present in such a resource in order to produce the kind of learning impact looked forward to in the learner.

Some of the characteristics a quality instructional resource should possess include being a content-rich-matter, that is, it should be able to give further information and make learning permanent in the learner, aligned to standard of being called instructional resource such that it is accessible and not bias, it should support pedagogy and evaluation. Furthermore, Angie (2024) says that a quality instructional resource should display relevance, clarity, engage learners, be durable, be adaptable to varying situations and conditions, be interactive, accuracy should be sure, it should be appealing, capable of generating feedback among others, show cultural diversity (culturally sensitive), motivating, ease of integration, be cost effective. For Carey (2024) such instructional resources should bear the following- be engaging, challenging and useable, it should be able to reduce teachers work and ease learners anxiety, and that its use should help in the explanation of the sequence of a given content for use. The features mostly are aimed at enhancing the learning potential of the learners such that with ease learning contents are meaningful and makes sense to such persons by producing traceable capacities in their training to become full and functional persons in the society for the society.

Training could be viewed as a process of exposing people or a person to a deliberately designed content for gaining knowledge and for acquiring skills. Amadioha and Akor (2019) sees training as a methodically designed way for persons in training to learn something new or improve on the older knowledge and skills they had. It was added that trainings are usually specific and targeted towards certain aims for empowerment, thus, teacher training is targeted or aimed towards such empowerment too. Therefore, teacher training could be construed as a methodical approach aimed towards empowering teachers to be effective and efficient in designated areas of their professional practice. In this case, the

teacher is being trained on how to apply pedagogical knowledge and skills with the help of available instructional resources in the teaching and learning process.

Based on the description given by (Kaira & Bhatia, 2008) training is a process intended towards improvement or an addition for knowledge and skills in order for the recipient to perform better. According to (Chand, n.d.) training could take any of this forms-induction, instructor-led training, apprenticeship training, soft skills development etc. However, the teacher training process occurs in the form of instructor-led training which takes place in the classroom. Here, the teacher and the learners are open to question and answer session (Vanny, 2016). This is the type adopted in the teacher education practice.

Teacher education is an act of preparing and equipping teachers for their future job. Akor et al (2024) say it is the process of specifically producing teachers today for their job tomorrow. This idea above is presented as a means through which teachers get trained but the emphasis is on the fact that their job for tomorrow is the concern, in other words, while they may be getting their training today the focus should be on how they can be amenable for relevance tomorrow, thus, innovation is required in the training process in order to make it akin to what is expected of them in the future. Perhaps, the reason Atuzie and Akor (2024) say that teacher education is for shaping in professional knowledge and skills, and sharpening of pedagogical skills in order to develop in the teacher trainee with what he needs to function better tomorrow.

The essence of this cannot be far from the intent of preparing a person for the life of tomorrow through exposure to mechanisms that are sustainability inclined and would enhance capability, and competence for a long time to come and this is what being relevant in educational practice entails especially when it comes to the issue of quality, particularly, in the area of instructional materials/resources, essentially, because the world of classroom instruction keeps evolving. This is so because the process of instruction deals with display of activities engaged in by the teacher and the learners in the classroom setting (Wordu and Akor, 2018). This is necessary for both the teacher and the learners to have a fruitful and worthwhile time together but as observed, the output does not always come as expected and so it is viewed that the reason is owed to not having the right level of homework done by the teacher. Thus, the question, what is responsible? While the challenge could be traceable to many factors like teacher factors, learner factors, the method used for teaching, nature of the environment, the use or non-use of instructional resources and even the quality of the instructional resource used cannot be left out.

According to sampled opinion from among teacher education students in a named university, it was discovered that their lecturers use instructional resources but the quality of such instructional resources in use does not seem to satisfy the need desired as projected by lecturers and this makes the said lecturer to keep explaining ideas over and again just to drive home the main objectives to be taught and this they would have just achieved by utilizing quality instructional resources to pass information on to the learners' through proper learning experience without much ado but as reported by the students, even after such long explanations, they end up not following and that the teacher trainers themselves do not care whether they followed or not on the lessons delivered, so, the point is left not understood, a fact that indicated that learning may not have taken place in such a situation as the students would not have got any information on which to unleash their critical thinking skills, make their learning permanent or even develop creativity skills for future learning. Hence, this research on impact of quality of instructional resource on teacher training process. Specifically, the study sought to achieve these objectives:

1. Determine the impact of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process.
2. Determine the output of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process.

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the impact of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process?
2. What is the output of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process?

RESEARCH METHOD

The study was carried out in Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria. The population for the study was made up of 550 students drawn from the department of Social Science Education (Social Studies, Economics and Geography) in the faculty of education of the University. The sample for the study was made up of 100 students drawn using the disproportionate random sampling technique, the sample size consisted of the various subgroups as stated above. The instrument used by the researchers for data collection was a questionnaire titled: Questionnaire on Review of Quality of Instructional Resource on Teacher Training Process (QRQIRTTP) which was constructed by the researchers. It consisted of 18-items which were arranged in two sections A and B. Section A contains the biodata, while section B consists of two subgroups on impact of quality instructional resource and output of quality instructional resource on students. The questionnaire was built on a modified four-point Likert Scale, namely: Very High Quality (VHQ), High Quality (HQ), Low Quality (LQ) and Very Low Quality (VLQ) and the levels of responses are weighted as 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively. The instrument was face validated by three experts; one from Measurement and Evaluation Unit, one Educational Technology unit and the other from Curriculum and Instruction unit of the Department of Educational Foundations of Prince Abubakar Audu University and Rivers State University, Nkpolu Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The suggestions given were used in producing the final copy of the instrument. Thereafter, 10 copies were administered on 300 level students in Rivers State University, Nkpolu-Port Harcourt. Cronbach Alpha was used in calculating the reliability which gave an alpha value of 0.83 which was considered high. The instrument was administered and collected by the researchers who guided the respondents. The data obtained were analyzed using, mean and standard deviation. Hence, $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5$. Therefore, items whose mean were less than 2.5 were seen as low quality (LQ) responses while those whose mean were 2.5 and above were seen as high quality (HQ) responses.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation on Impact of a Quality Instructional Resource on Teacher Training Process

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	N	Remark
1.	Space for resource	1.9	1.3	LQ	100
2.	Portability of resource	3.2	0.22	HQ	100
3.	Safety of resource	2.1	0.95	LQ	100
4.	Encoding of resource	3.0	0.28	HQ	100
5.	Information property of resource	3.4	0.17	HQ	100
6.	Versatility of resource	3.3	0.17	HQ	100
7.	Information note on resource	3.5	0.24	HQ	100
	Grand Mean and S D	2.91	0.47		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The results on table 1 above indicated high quality impact of a quality of instructional resource on teacher training process as affirmed by the grand mean (2.91). The impact of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process was rated to be of high quality with information notes on resources, information property, versatility of resource, portality of resource and encoding of resource with leading mean score while safety of resource and space for the resource were rated low quality with lower mean score. This simply means that there is low quality impact of the instructional resource when it comes to the space and safety of the resources. The implication is that instructional resources to be used for instructional purpose should express high quality in order for it to achieve the desired results.

Research Question 2: *What is the output of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on Output of a Quality Instructional Resource on Teacher Training Process

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	N	Remark
1.	Task variables of resource	3.3	0.17	HQ	100
2.	Learner variables of resource	2.2	0.45	LQ	100
3.	Background knowledge of resource	3.5	0.24	HQ	100
4.	Knowledge of teacher of the resource	3.4	0.17	HQ	100
5.	Knowledge of curriculum on resource	3.2	0.22	HQ	100
6.	Knowledge of prevailing situation of resource	2.1	0.95	LQ	100
7.	Performance of resource	3.5	0.24	HQ	100
	Grand Mean and S D	3.02	0.34		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The result on table 2 showed the output of high quality instructional resource on teacher training process with grand mean (3.02). The output result showed that background of the resource and performance of resource received the highest quality rating, followed by others as knowledge of the teacher of the resource, tasks variables of resource and knowledge of curriculum but the output of the learner variables resource and knowledge of prevailing situation resource were rated as being of low quality. The implication is that learner variables are not completely covered with the use of quality instructional resource perhaps depending on the knowledge of the teacher of how to use the instructional resource and even the knowledge of curriculum for enhanced output of the instructional resource.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The result on table 1 above showed that there was a positive response to the impact of quality of instructional resource on teacher training process. This is affirmed based on the grand mean obtained which was high enough. However, it is necessary to state that high quality rating was given to information notes on resources, information property, versatility of resource, portality of resource and encoding of

resource while safety of resource and space for the resource had low quality rating. This is indicative of the fact that the resources used in instructional delivery hold high potential when it comes to the quality of such resources. Nonetheless, the space occupied and the safety of the resources could not be guaranteed based on the result reported. This may not be far from the challenge of adequate accommodation for the resource and that of theft within the environment where the resource is kept. In a study carried out by Arop, Umanah & Effiong (2015) the result of the present study was confirmed as it was found that the use of quality instructional resource leads to favourable students' achievement in science subjects. Again, Senyamentor, Amponsah, Nutifala & Edjah (2022) found that use of quality instructional resource predicts effectiveness in teacher preparation. Moreso, Tyton Partner (2022) discovered after a study that quality instructional resources enhance teacher quality and experience on how to go in curriculum delivery process. The implication of this is to note that quality instructional resources enhance effectiveness of teacher training process but it is also important that accommodation be provided for the resources and theft checking processes arranged by the school management to deal with such tendencies. Next, the result on table 2 showed the output of a quality instructional resource on teacher training process. The output result indicated that background of the resource and performance of resource received the high quality rating and others that had better rating include knowledge of the teacher of the resource, tasks variables of resource and knowledge of curriculum but the output of the learner variables resource and knowledge of prevailing situation resource were rated as being of low quality output. This may not be unconnected with the teacher not having adequate knowledge of the learner factors and to apply them in curriculum implementation process. Also, knowledge of prevailing situation is vital at helping the teacher educator to contextualize instructional resource during use in a classroom situation. Thus, the findings of (Terry, 2017; Okeke & Ajadi, 2023; Miller, & Partelow, 2019) found that high quality instructional resource drive teachers' growth in professional practice leading to improved student outcome. It was also, discovered that quality instructional resource influence instructional delivery in public schools in primary schools in Nigeria. Furthermore, it was found that high quality instructional resource utilization brings about improvement in students achievement. The implication of the above is that high quality instructional resource should be encouraged for use by the school for teacher training process and it is important that teachers should have good knowledge of learners under them as well as the circumstance of the classroom setting.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion that could be drawn from the findings of the study is that the use of quality instructional resource in teacher training process enhances effectiveness and leads to better achievement among students in teacher training process. Moreso, adequate space should be made available for resource storage and security put in place to check theft. It was also discovered that the teachers who use instructional resource must be aware of learner variables in order to deliver lesson to the learner adequately as the well as the ability to contextualize instructional resource.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The teacher education managers should do well to ensure that adequate space is provided for the storage of instructional resources for future use
2. The school management is also encouraged to put security in place to avert the theft of instructional resources provided for teaching and learning process.
3. Teacher educators should do well to be knowledgeable in learner variables in order to have a high performing class of students.
4. It is also encouraged that teacher educators should be familiar with prevailing resources in the area in order to creatively contextualize instructional resource for use in classroom situation.
5. The government should support the funding of quality instructional resource provision for use in teacher training process.

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